

Joker's Laughter Complex or Pseudobulbar Affect?

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Abstract

This paper begins with a case of a 10-year-old autistic child, who exhibits unpredictable laughter for no obvious reason, to the embarrassment of his parents, especially when the family is in the public area. What is known as the Joker's Laughter Complex - a form of psychological complex - is a rarely understood condition of pseudobulbar affect (PBA).

Keywords: Center for Neurologic Study Liability Scale, Joker's Laughter Complex, Pseudobulbar Affect, Psychological Complex

The Joker's Laughter Complex

It has been noticed there are times when we notice atypically developed children, adolescents and even adults just laugh uncontrollably and/or inappropriately in any context. Known as the Joker's Laughter Complex (JLC), which is a form of psychological complex¹ (Jung, 1933), the character Joker - created by Bill Finger, Bob Kane, and Jerry Robinson in the DC Comics - is portrayed as a super-villain. The Joker's character made his first appearance in the inaugural issue of Batman on April 25, 1940. As a criminal mastermind, the character is the polar opposite of Batman in both personality and appearance. Initially introduced as a psychopathic character with a twisted, sadistic sense of humor, the Joker was re-imagined as a comical prankster in the late 1950s due to Comics Code Authority regulations. However, the character of Joker returned to his darker, more sinister nature in the early 1970s.

According to Carl Jung, a psychological complex is a cluster of related thoughts, feelings, and memories that are organized around a central theme or experience, often stemming from unconscious material (Jung, 1933). These complexes are emotional and psychological structures that can influence an individual's behavior, perceptions, and interactions. They arise from personal experiences and are typically rooted in unresolved conflicts or significant life events. Jung believed that complexes operate outside of conscious awareness and can affect one's thoughts and actions in powerful ways, often causing emotional distress or influencing decisions and relationships.

This psychological condition of Joker's Laughter Complex (JLC) is similar to another condition known as Pseudobulbar affect (PBA), which is a neurological condition characterized by uncontrollable episodes of laughing or crying that are disproportionate or inappropriate to the situation. In this paper, the authors use the two terms JLC and PBA interchangeably as the same condition. These emotional outbursts are involuntary and

¹ Jung (1921, 1933) highlighted the crucial role of the unconscious in shaping personality. He suggested that the unconscious is composed of two layers. The first layer, known as the personal unconscious, closely parallels Freud's concept of the unconscious. This personal unconscious encompasses both forgotten information and repressed memories, which influence an individual's psychological complexes and overall behavior.

do not match an individual's actual feelings. PBA often occurs in people with certain neurological conditions or brain injuries, where the ability of the brain to control emotional expression is disrupted. According to Moore et al. (1997), "[A]long with depression many patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS; Black, 1982; Davison & Kelman, 1939; McDonald et al., 1994) have sudden outbursts of uncontrollable laughter or tearfulness known variously as affective or emotional lability, pseudobulbar emotionality, or pathological laughter and crying. Such outbursts can occur spontaneously or in response to provocative stimuli such as questions or events" (p. 89).

Key Symptoms of Pseudobulbar Affect (PBA)

The primary symptoms of PBA are (i) sudden and unpredictable episodes of laughing, crying, or both; (ii) these outbursts can occur without any trigger or may be out of proportion to the stimulus that caused them; and (iii) the laughing or crying episodes are usually brief but can be distressing and socially disruptive (see Figure 1). It is crucial to take note that PBA does not reflect an individual's true emotional state. For instance, a child might cry when s/he is not sad or laugh in a situation that is not funny.

Figure 1. Symptomatology of Pseudobulbar Affect (PBA)

Any Relation to Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Psychosis?

PBA is distinct from psychiatric conditions like autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and psychosis. However, it can coexist with these two conditions, often leading to a diagnostic confusion and even misdiagnosis. Individuals with ASD do exhibit sudden laughter or crying without any link to the immediate context and often parents and teachers wonder what could have trigger that unexplainable behavior. ASD, a developmental disorder, involves challenges with social interaction, communication, and repetitive behaviors but does not inherently include uncontrollable emotional outbursts like those seen in PBA. Regardless, autistic individuals may display unusual emotional responses, which could be mistaken for PBA.

Psychosis, characterized by a disconnection from reality, may include emotional disturbances, but these are typically linked to delusions or hallucinations. In contrast, PBA is strictly related to neurological disruption rather than a break with reality. However, when PBA occurs in individuals with conditions like multiple sclerosis, traumatic brain injury, or stroke, it can sometimes be misinterpreted as a psychiatric issue.

How is Pseudobulbar Affect (PBA) formally assessed?

Assessing PBA involves a careful neurological evaluation to distinguish it from psychiatric disorders. Tools like the Center for Neurologic Study-Lability Scale (CNS-LS; Moore et al., 1997) are used to quantify the frequency and severity of the episodes. The CNS-LS has been validated in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and multiple sclerosis (MS) patient populations (Moore et al., 1997; Smith et al., 2004). Recently, a Chinese translation of the assessment tool has been made available by Chen et al. (2024). In addition, it is important to have a detailed history of the patient's medical background, including any neurological disorders or brain injuries, is crucial for an

accurate diagnosis. Additionally, input from family members or caregivers can provide valuable context regarding the nature and impact of the episodes.

Treatment for Pseudobulbar Affect

Generally, the treatment for PBA involves medication. The most commonly prescribed drugs are dextromethorphan/quinidine (Nuedexta), which is specifically approved for PBA, and antidepressants such as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) or tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs). These medications help to regulate neurotransmitter activity in the brain to reduce the frequency and intensity of emotional outbursts. Non-pharmacological approaches, such as behavioral therapy, psychotherapy and counseling, may also be beneficial, particularly in helping individuals and their families manage the social and psychological effects of PBA.

Conclusion

PBA can significantly impact quality of life, but with proper diagnosis and treatment, individuals can often achieve better control over their emotional responses.

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